

SENIOR HIGH STUDENTS' AWARENESS, CONCERN AND PRACTICES TOWARD CLIMATE CHANGE

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to determine the awareness, concern and practices to climate change. The respondents of the study were the 212 Grade 11 students of Demetrio L. Alviola National High School – Senior High School Department for school year 2023-2024. The researcher utilized a descriptive-survey design, used an adapted questionnaire and employed weighted mean. The findings of the study revealed that students are “very aware” on climate change. They have “very high” concern towards climate change and exhibited “high” when it comes to practices in combatting climate change. It was also revealed that the sources of information about climate change were “utilized” such as social media, school and internet browsing.

Keywords: *climate change, awareness, concern, practices*

INTRODUCTION

Challenging issues surrounding climate change demand attention (IPCC, 2023). Udenyi (2010) highlighted that climate change refers to significant and measurable shifts in global temperatures, which are believed to be on a continual rise.

The Public Health Institute and Center for Climate Change and Health (2016) reported that 97% of climate scientists concur that climate change is happening and is primarily driven by human activity. Uzoechi (2009) observed that humans have been altering their

environment in profound ways since learning to hunt with weapons, domesticate animals, and cultivate crops. This trend has been further accelerated by advancements in modern transportation and industrial systems, enabling easier movement and production.

Riedy (2016) examined the observable and projected climate changes, including higher temperatures, altered rainfall patterns, and shifts in the frequency and distribution of extreme weather events like droughts, storms, floods, and heatwaves. These changes, along with sea-level rise, have profound effects on human and ecological systems.

Omosho (2007), Ishaya & Obaja (2008), Anyadike (2009), and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2010) contended that human activities—such as bush burning, deforestation, and the relentless burning of fossil fuels—contribute to the excessive emission of greenhouse gases. The degree of awareness about the role of these activities in climate change significantly influences their continuation. Jacobo (2021) added that for any lingering doubts about climate change, the Arctic provides undeniable evidence. The region is warming at twice the global rate, leading to the alarming melting of sea ice, permafrost, and ice caps, which serve as critical regulators of the planet's temperature.

Tropical cyclones, also called typhoons or hurricanes, are among the most devastating weather phenomena. The Philippines, one of the most typhoon-prone countries globally, experiences approximately 20 tropical cyclones annually (United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, 2022). On December 16, 2021, Super Typhoon Rai (locally known as Odette) struck the Philippines, causing torrential rains, violent winds, floods, and storm surges in the Visayas and Mindanao Islands. It left thousands of families homeless, disrupted the country's COVID-19 recovery progress, and inflicted widespread damage to infrastructure and services in more than seven provinces.

The Integrated Disaster Science and Management: Global Case Studies in Mitigation and Recovery (2018) noted a strong consensus that anthropogenic climate change is contributing to stronger typhoons. Rising sea surface and subsurface temperatures eliminate the natural buffers that cold ocean water provides against typhoon intensification. Additionally, sea-level rise exacerbates the impacts of these storms, leaving densely populated regions like the Philippines increasingly vulnerable.

UNESCO (2015) emphasized that climate change education (CCE) is a pivotal tool in addressing climate-related challenges. Chang and Pascua (2017) advocated for implementing CCE in formal educational settings, such as schools and universities. This approach allows students to engage in discussions about climate change, fostering informed decisions about consumption, lifestyle, and strategies for mitigation and adaptation.

Wackernagel & Rees (2007) stressed the importance of enhancing environmental awareness and climate literacy among citizens to reduce their ecological footprint. This footprint represents the total land area required to provide the resources consumed and absorb the waste and pollution generated by individuals or communities, such as schools.

In the context of climate change, schools play a critical role in raising awareness and equipping students with strategies to understand the connection between their choices and environmental impacts. By fostering critical thinking and instilling a sense of responsibility, schools can nurture active sustainability and enhance climate literacy (Gottlieb et al, 2012).

A climate-literate individual possesses a strong understanding of the earth's climate system, evaluates credible scientific information about climate change, communicates this knowledge effectively, and makes informed decisions (Cartea & Vinuesa, 2021).

Given these pressing challenges, this research aims to assess the levels of awareness, concern, and practices related to climate change. Its findings will be particularly impactful for the youth, empowering them to take an active role in protecting the environment and addressing the ongoing climate crisis.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of students about climate change?
2. What is the level of concern of students on climate change?
3. What is the level of practice taken by students on climate change?
4. What is the level of utilization of sources of climate change information among students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a descriptive survey design. It aimed to determine the awareness, concern and practices by the students including their sources of information in dealing with climate change.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in Demetrio L. Alviola National High School – Senior High School (DLANHS-SHS) Department which is located at Bindoy, Negros Oriental, Philippines.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the randomly selected Grade 11 students from Demetrio L. Alviola National High School – Senior High School Department of school year 2023-2024 who were coming from the 9 Senior High Strands. Slovin's formula was used in determining the sample size. Of the 451 total population, only 212 students were considered as part of the study.

Accountancy, Business and Management	20
Humanities and Social Sciences	57
Science, Technology, Engineering & Mathematics	15
Organic Agriculture	26
Tourism	18
Bread & Pastry Production	12
Computer Systems Servicing	21
Electrical Installation & Maintenance	22
Shield Metal Arc Welding	22
Total	212

Research Instrument

The study utilized an adapted survey questionnaire (Lopez & Malay, 2019). The questionnaire is divided into four parts.

Part I consisted the awareness level of the students towards climate change. Part II identified the concernment of students towards climate change. Part III determined the practices taken on climate change. Meanwhile, Part IV consisted of sources of information regarding climate change.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher submitted a letter to the Public Schools District Supervisor of Bindoy District II and Principal of DLANHS-SHS for approval. After the approval was granted, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to the respondents where the purpose and goal of the study were explained. The questionnaires were collected after the students answered them. The results were tallied using MS Excel software.

Data Analysis

The study utilized a quantitative approach where the collected data were analyzed using weighted mean in order to get the extent of awareness, concern, practices including the sources of information on climate change.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1
Awareness of Grade 11 Students Towards Climate Change

Indicators	\bar{w}_x	Description
1. Climate change refers to long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns.	3.33	VHA
2. Global warming is an increase in the Earth's average surface temperature.	3.34	VHA
3. Burning of fossil fuels causes climate change.	3.20	HA
4. Carbon dioxide is a greenhouse gas.	2.96	HA
5. Cutting down trees contribute to climate change.	3.38	VHA
6. Sea level continue to rise due to climate change.	2.97	HA
7. Climate change can cause polar ice caps and glaciers to melt.	2.81	HA
8. Climate change can cause more floods and drought.	3.23	HA
9. Climate change creates stronger typhoons.	3.26	VHA
10. Shifting to renewable energy can help solve our rising global temperature.	3.07	HA
Composite	3.16	HA

Scale	Verbal Description
3.26 – 4.00	Very Highly Aware (VHA)
2.51 – 3.25	Highly Aware (HA)
1.76 – 2.50	Slightly Aware (SA)
1.00 – 1.75	Not Aware (NA)

Table 1 shows the level of awareness of the grade 11 students regarding climate change. Overall, the students were found to be highly aware with a composite mean of 3.16. The result also indicated that the students are very highly aware on the statements: cutting down trees contribute to climate change, global warming increases the Earth's average surface temperature and that climate change creates stronger typhoons.

Trott (2024) emphasized that education plays a vital role in enhancing learners' understanding of climate change. It serves as a cornerstone for fostering an informed and active public, capable of comprehending, addressing, and caring about the complexities and inequities of the climate crisis. Many have highlighted that knowledge is the essential starting point for deeper involvement. Similarly, Hendryx et al. (2013) noted that increased awareness can significantly influence individuals' decision-making, advocacy initiatives, and efforts to promote more equitable and sustainable environmental practices within their communities or organizations.

Table 2
Concern of Grade 11 Students Towards Climate Change

Indicators	\bar{w}_x	Description	Equivalent
1. I believe that climate change is real.	3.73	SA	EC
2. I believe that climate change is a serious environmental problem.	3.61	SA	EC
3. I am hopeful that there are practices that we can do to lessen the effects of climate change.	3.39	SA	EC
4. I believe that immediate actions should be done about climate change.	3.22	A	VC
5. I am preparing myself for the effects of climate change.	3.39	SA	EC
6. I always ask questions about climate change.	3.08	A	VC
7. I rethink my actions considering they contribute to climate change.	3.05	A	VC
8. I actively participate in the discussion when it comes to climate change.	3.19	A	VC
9. I am seriously concerned with climate change and its effects to mankind.	3.56	SA	EC
10. I deeply care for the future of our planet	3.57	SA	EC
Composite	3.38	SA	EC

Scale	Verbal Description	Equivalent
3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Extremely Concerned (EC)
2.51 – 3.25	Agree (A)	Very Concerned (VC)
1.76 – 2.50	Disagree (D)	Slightly Concerned (SC)
1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Not at all Concerned (NC)

Table 2 presents the concern responses of students on climate change. As reflected, the respondents strongly agree with composite mean of 3.38 which means that they are extremely concerned about climate change.

Ramos et al. (2024) highlighted in their study that students are inclined to adopt more environmentally conscious behaviors to contribute to improving the environment. Brennan (2014) argued that environmental degradation can be mitigated through the development of moral behaviors and ethical attitudes toward nature. Similarly, research by Simpao and Yabut (2022) involving university students in Metro Manila, Philippines, demonstrated that attitudes significantly influence their behaviors related to environmental conservation.

Table 3
Practices of Grade 11 Students Towards Climate Change

Indicators	\bar{w}_x	Description	Equivalent
1. I participate in climate change related advocacies and activities.	3.15	O	H
2. I reduce the amount of waste I create.	3.15	O	H
3. I use things more than once.	3.19	O	H
4. I recycle materials instead of throwing them.	3.24	O	H
5. I save electricity by turning off electrical devices that are not in use.	3.33	A	VH
6. I use social media to share climate change related information.	2.99	O	H
7. I talk to my friends and family to do their part in solving climate change.	2.90	O	H
8. I segregate my trash.	3.29	A	VH
9. I repair things instead of buying a new one.	3.26	A	VH
10. I walk or use bicycle instead of riding a vehicle.	2.99	O	H
Composite	3.15	O	H

Scale	Verbal Description	Equivalent
3.26 – 4.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
2.51 – 3.25	Often (O)	High (H)
1.76 – 2.50	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.75	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 3 shows the practices taken among students in continuing the fight against climate change. As illustrated in the table, the composite mean is 3.15 which means that the students have taken high practices in helping to be part of the solution against this pressing environmental problem. It can be noted that saving electricity when not in use, segregating their trash and repairing things instead of buying a new one obtained very high level of practices.

The findings align with those of Khorasgani and Tavakoli (2024), who reported that most students have taken personal actions to reduce their carbon footprint. Their analysis revealed that younger students demonstrate greater support for climate actions. Similarly, Composto and Weber (2022) highlighted an expanding body of behavioral science research focused on intervention strategies to promote sustainable behaviors, such as recycling, using public transportation, and conserving household energy.

Jones et al. (2017) observed that communication strategies aimed at reducing the psychological distance of climate change—by making it feel more immediate in terms of

geography, society, and time—effectively increased climate concern and strengthened self-reported intentions to adopt mitigating behaviors like reducing energy use. Additionally, Fucio et al. (2023) emphasized the necessity of implementing comprehensive waste management and collection guidelines at Laguna University. These guidelines should aim to optimize waste management practices, enhance efficiency, and establish a more systematic approach to handling waste. Equally important is the need to raise awareness, making waste collection an integral part of daily life not only within the university but also at home and across the broader community.

Table 4
Utilization of Sources of Information on Climate Change

Indicators	\bar{w}_x	Description	Equivalent
1. Books	2.97	O	U
2. Internet Browsing	3.45	A	FU
3. Family and Relatives	3.33	A	FU
4. Friends and Acquaintances	3.01	O	U
5. Magazines	2.48	R	MU
6. Movies	2.96	O	U
7. Newspapers	2.53	O	U
8. Social Media	3.64	A	FU
9. Television	3.48	A	FU
10. School	3.58	A	FU
Composite	3.14	O	U

Scale	Verbal Description	Equivalent
3.26 – 4.00	Always (A)	Fully Utilized (FU)
2.51 – 3.25	Often (O)	Utilized (U)
1.76 – 2.50	Rarely (R)	Minimally Utilized (MU)
1.00 – 1.75	Never (N)	Not Utilized (NU)

Table 4 displays the respondents' sources of information on climate change. The students. It was revealed that the level of utilization among the sources of information on climate change is "utilized" which means that the students have utilized the common sources of information in knowing more about climate change. It further revealed that social media, school and television were among the top 3 fully utilized sources of information.

Barreda (2018) supported the findings of the current study by identifying education, mass media, family, training programs, seminar workshops, the internet, and social media as key channels for enhancing climate change awareness. Similarly, Lineman et al. (2015)

noted that greater awareness of climate change is linked to exposure through social media networks, which frequently publicize the term. They emphasized that the primary driver of increased awareness is the heightened publicity surrounding climate change, whether portrayed positively or negatively.

Nayle et al. (2024) highlighted the pivotal role educational institutions play in fostering ethical values and environmental awareness among students

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were hereby drawn:

1. The level of awareness of Grade 11 students on climate change is high.
2. The level of concern of the senior high students towards climate change is very high.
3. The level of practice taken by the students in combatting the fight against climate change is high.
4. The level of utilization on sources of climate change information is utilized.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended:

1. School leaders must advocate in the integration of climate change in the delivery of instruction. They must ensure that teachers design meaningful instructional materials for the improvement of knowledge.
2. Sustain the concern and practices taken by students by allowing them to be immersed in environmental activities in and outside the campus to continue nurturing their love for the planet.
3. Increase exposure to different sources of information on climate change to deepen their learning experiences on the issue.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher adhered to ethical standards throughout the study. Information consents were obtained from the respondents. The data collected were treated with confidentiality and anonymity.

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